

J-MASS AND CONCURRENT SIMULATION IN THE LABORATORY ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Changes in simulation technology now allow the creation of virtual prototypes of conceptual hardware systems in advance of when actual hardware could be built. This paper discusses the concept and vision of employing the Joint Modeling and Simulation System in an Air Force laboratory environment for desktop collaborative virtual prototyping. The development of a digital model in parallel with the hardware is concurrent simulation. The model becomes more detailed as the conceptual system and design evolve and as the hardware technology moves from breadboard to brassboard to flyable prototype. The digital model is then transitioned with the hardware technology for further engineering and manufacturing development into a deployable system. Virtual prototyping and concurrent simulation are key tools for the future of Air Force research and development. This paper addresses how such tools can be employed and utilized in the laboratory.

VIRTUAL PROTOTYPING IN INDUSTRY

Virtual prototyping is used in the commercial sector today. Hardware/software co-design and virtual prototyping, using hardware design languages such as VHDL, have been very successful in digital system design. Their success is demonstrated by and the ever improving capabilities of microcomputer chips that are faster, smaller, cheaper and with short time-to-market cycles. The aerospace industry demonstrated the success of integrated computer assisted design with supporting modeling and simulation in bringing the new Boeing 777 airliner to market. A complete model of the plane allowed design teams to walk through the virtual prototype to see how the components were changing. The virtual prototype served as a common frame of reference for the designers, engineers, and managers. Similarly, the automotive industry has used CAD and modeling for years as an integral part of the design process. Advanced three dimensional visualization systems using virtual reality technology help automotive designers and engineers evaluate virtual prototypes of products without building physical prototypes. Virtual prototypes of car exteriors and interiors allow engineers to walk around and sit inside a virtual car. For some companies, a common virtual design and manufacturing environment permits the collaboration of engineers in geographically dispersed sites. Advances in software and computer technology are making Desktop Collaborative Virtual Prototyping possible and affordable

for the engineering process in government and industry research.

THE JOINT SYNTHETIC BATTLESPACE

The Air Force envisions an integrated, common modeling and simulation (M&S) environment that will be accessed by analysts, warfighters, developers, and testers supporting the range of Air Force tasks, from determining requirements through conducting operations. The key concept in the Air Force M&S vision is the Joint Synthetic Battlespace -- an integrated M&S environment where simulations extend from high level aggregate models to detailed engineering models, from pilots in live aircraft and simulators to hardware components and laboratory test beds (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Joint Synthetic Battlespace

Such a system allows the user to selectably choose the level of detail needed for the task at hand, draw on distant resources, and easily "plug-and-play" computer simulations, manned simulators, and live hardware to create any needed simulation environment. Analysts, researchers, decision makers, and warfighters must be able to "plug in" to a common battlespace from their desks, simulators, or crew stations in order to assess, develop, train, or conduct warfighting. Demonstrations of a future system's military worth will be conducted in the synthetic environment represented by the Joint Battlespace. The underlying M&S technology also offers an opportunity for the research community to implement concurrent simulation and desktop collaborative virtual prototyping. The Joint Modeling and

Simulation System (J-MASS) is a key enabling technology for concurrent simulation.

CONCURRENT SIMULATION THROUGHOUT THE DEFENSE SYSTEM LIFE CYCLE

Historically, program requirements are difficult to quantify and verbalize. A user is able to state what he/she doesn't want much easier than describing what he/she does want. A simulation model developed in parallel with the hardware or technology development allows the scientist, engineer, or end user to refine system requirements early in the engineering process. Current Air Force directives, embodied in the Air Force Test and Evaluation Process, include a requirement to create a digital representation of the system under development (Digital System Model) that must be updated and maintained throughout the life cycle of the system. The Digital System Model (DSM) is essentially a virtual prototype of the real world system under development. A virtual prototype allows the engineer to see the impact of design changes. Trade studies using the model can then be performed throughout development as an essential part of the systems engineering process. The Air Force envisions that the Digital System Models will be compliant with J-MASS as the common M&S environment for acquisition and development.

The virtual prototyping can start even earlier in the research and development process -- within the laboratory. A technology model can be developed in parallel with the laboratory's hardware technology as shown in Figure 2. The technology model becomes more detailed as the conceptual system and design evolve and as the technology moves from breadboard to brassboard to flyable prototype.

Figure 2. Virtual Prototyping in the Laboratory

The evolving hardware is used to validate the computer model and the model is used to extrapolate hardware test

results. The technology model is then transitioned with the hardware technology to the System Program Office (SPO) for Engineering and Manufacturing Development (EMD). The SPO continues development of the computer model in parallel with the hardware. The virtual prototype can be employed on virtual test ranges or virtual proving grounds as part of the Test Process. Ultimately, a computer model of the full production system is fielded with the operational system for use in OT&E and later deployment.

COLLABORATIVE VIRTUAL PROTOTYPING

The current DoD and Air Force vision is common M&S to support technology assessment, system upgrade, prototype and full-scale development, and force structuring. There will be more Joint activities among the Services and agencies and increased dual use applications between the defense and commercial sectors. As the downsizing trends continue in both defense and industry, the military and commercial laboratories will increasingly depend on other organizations for key technologies to integrate into systems. A current working definition of Collaborative Virtual Prototyping (CVP) is the application of advanced information systems technology in design, modeling, simulation, analysis, manufacturing, testing, and logistics to support life cycle development of a system in a geographically distributed electronic environment. Collaborative virtual prototyping will become a crucial means of sharing technology and systems integration as shown in Figure 3. CVP will assist in the breakdown of technology stovepipes and become the construct for communication of technologies between domains.

Figure 3. Collaboration Across Domains

CVP can be implemented in many organizational structures, for example, traditional hierarchical workplaces, concurrent engineering environments, and work groups focused on

rapid prototyping. Implementation requires attention to the necessary enabling technologies and supporting infrastructure and possible changes in the engineering paradigm. The enabling technologies required for a CVP engineering environment include

- computer network - a distributed computing environment across a heterogeneous network
- object standards and services- Common Object Request Broker Architecture (CORBA) interface standard is today's leading commercial standard
- software services - applications, data services, and M&S environment

Figure 4. Distributed Collaborative Virtual Prototyping

A crucial part of implementation is education of personnel on how CVP can meet customer, organizational, and individual goals, and benefits such as decreased time-to-market, lowered life cycle cost, and product quality improvement.

As the Virtual Prototype Marketplace evolves, industry will build commercial tools to work with Joint and commercial standards in response to real customer demand as in

Figure 5. Virtual Prototype Marketplace

Figure 5. Joint M&S Standards, such as J-MASS, are designed as Open Systems Architectures with the capability to be expanded by the addition of site specific software, including COTS. The Joint M&S Standards serve as a GOTS framework for the addition of third party applications. J-MASS brings a common M&S environment which provides

- Open systems architecture supporting applications conforming to commercial and industry standards
- Visual paradigm -- visual programming and visualization of output results
- Object based to allow component reuse
- Extensible architecture for future software concepts
- Execution on distributed heterogeneous network of workstations
- Tools to support development of model components
- Multiple language support
- Tools and models support a "Plug and Play" concept
- Supports "distributed model development" by the domain experts
- Provide a repository of models and their components

SUMMARY

Advances in software and computer technology are making Desktop Collaborative Virtual Prototyping possible and affordable for the engineering process in government and industry research. Collaborative virtual prototyping will become a crucial means of sharing technology and systems integration for research and development and is a natural extension of the Air Force vision for an integrated, common M&S environment accessed by analysts, researchers, warfighters, developers, and testers.